

The Effectiveness Of An Educational Environment Based Gamification Strategy Through An Educational Platform In The Acquisition Of Scientific Concepts And The Attitudes Towards Science

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 23, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 05, 2021</p> <p>Keywords: Gamification, Scientific Concepts, Attitudes towards science, Educational Platform</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4586909</p>	<p><i>The study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of an educational environment based on gamification strategy in scientific concepts acquisition, the attitudes toward science among second-grade students in Jordan. Participants of the study consisted of 44 students from the second grade primary students of the private Directorate Amman in the academic year (2020-2021), and they were divided randomly into a control group and experimental group. To achieve the study's objectives, the teacher's guide was prepared by the gamification strategy and the scientific concepts test preparation, which consisted of (22) multi-choice questions and the scale of attitudes toward the science scale. The results showed a statistically significant effect at the level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$) for the educational environment based on gamification strategy through the Microsoft Teams platform in acquiring scientific concepts and developing the attitudes toward science among second-grade students compared to the traditional method. The study recommended adopting the gamification strategy within educational environments in science education for all academic levels.</i></p>

Introduction

The world is currently facing an educational crisis due to the Corona pandemic, which calls for reconsidering traditional methods of teaching science and searching for modern techniques that ensure positive interaction for the learner, and his acquisition of scientific concepts in a way that enables him to benefit from them, especially in the lower primary stage. During this stage, the concepts acquired are considered one of the essential cognitive basics for the learner this stage's characteristics allow the learner to organize his concepts in a meaningful way. Developed and developing societies have been interested in science, so they emphasized teaching science in ways that reflect those subjects' nature and developing the content, educational methods of evaluation, and the science teachers (Ambu Saedi & Al Balushi, 2009).

Education is the developmental process of any country aimed at its renaissance (Mackatiani et al., 2016). Science occupies a privileged position among other subjects because it deals with natural phenomena. Science education plays a special role in all developed countries seeking to improve various aspects of life; this makes it imperative for educational specialists to strive towards developing science curricula, methods, and strategies for teaching them in a way that contributes to promoting continuous learning for all students, which is imposed by contemporary scientific and technological development (Schulze & Lemmer, 2017).

Khatayba (2008) emphasized the importance of teaching and learning concepts, which forms the basis of scientific knowledge, and necessitated the provision of an educational environment that helps students learn scientific concepts and develop their way of thinking, and also necessitated the presence of a science teacher who can use appropriate teaching methods to help the learner build the concepts (Nobes & Panagiotaki, 2007).

The scientific concept is defined as a mental image that a person creates about common characteristics of things or people he interacts with the environment. Concepts can serve as building blocks for more complex or abstract representations (Zirbel, 2006). Concepts grow with positive participation from the learner's interaction with the surrounding environment, and the school has a prominent role to play in preparing that participation in the educational situation so that their perceptions grow in the right direction (Kojak, 2006).

Concepts play an essential role in highlighting the importance of the academic material to the learner, as they link cognitive facts with strong ties through the qualities and characteristics of the concept. So they stay longer in mind due to their connection with their meaning, and they allow the organization and linking of groups of things to make them easier to understand and survive more than separate parts (Pabellon, 2005).

Zaitoun (2008) pointed out the consensus of educational studies and research on the ability of science teachers and the school to play an important role in developing scientific attitudes among students and encouraging them to develop an interest in science and increase their tendencies. Therefore, the science teacher should stimulate classroom learning motivation whereby science professionals suggest programs, scientific activities, and teaching methods that make the student effective and participate in the science education process.

Lyons (2006) showed that there is a decrease in attitudes toward science in particular, due to presenting science topics without attempting to link them with students' preferences and interests, and it showed the students' appreciation for their teachers, who have drawn for them the contexts of daily life. It also showed that males' attitudes were more positive than females' towards science, and their attitudes were less negative towards developing their attitudes. The study recommends using practical activities to increase students' experience in school science and improve their future attitudes towards science. Siegel & Ranney (2003) indicates that attitudes affect the persistence of performance. This study agrees with the study (Papanastasiou & Zembylas, 2002) that there is a positive correlation between scientific attitudes and scientific performance.

Learning science encourages students to deal with scientific ideas properly, enhances their imagination capabilities, and increases their motivation towards science and learning. Learning scientific concepts at the elementary level is considered one of the main goals of science learning, as it is the focus of the science curriculum, and learning scientific concepts increases the effectiveness of learning; this contributes to the possibility of students' performance on their knowledge and using it to generate new knowledge and solve problems. Researchers and educational specialists have given great importance to scientific concepts and have developed them according to various teaching strategies and methods (Hamadneh 2017), (Okedeyi, 2015).

Science education plays a vital role in people's lives and determines the extent of their progress because of this material's application value in our contemporary life. So it is necessary to spread the scientific culture among individuals, which includes the development of positive attitudes toward science being one of the most critical current perspectives in science education (Osborn, Simon & Collins, 2003). And Al-Subaie (2003) indicated that the rich physical environment increases students' attitudes toward school and work to raise their academic achievement and develop scientific attitudes through activities that challenge the student and his ideas. The use of e-learning in designing educational activities that help the student to acquire new experiences and virtual educational activities, in addition to that, helps him to imagine and create, making him a creative innovator capable of meeting the technological requirements of the future (Grable, Overbay, and Osborne, 2005).

One of the strategies that relied on technology and e-learning was gamification, as the gamification was formulated by the British programmer Nick Pelling (Macdonald, 2015), in which play is used in conditions other than playing without a goal. Its principles and ideas are used to develop interaction and integration through increased motivation, feedback, participation, and loyalty by its participants. This strategy is comprehensive through the intertwining of psychology, computers, video games, marketing, and so on (Swan, 2012). The strategy of gamification is to apply the principles of the game to engage students and motivate them to learn, as games are nowadays a part of students' daily life, and they spend a lot of time practicing them, which helps improve learning participation and provide more adaptive and appropriate learning for students (Mohamad, Sazali, and Salleh, 2017). As gamification stimulates students to engage in the classroom, it also gives teachers better tools to guide and reward students, and it blurs the lines between formal and informal learning, which in turn inspires students to learn in-depth and broadly for life (Lee & Hammer, 2011).

Gamification is an important tool that the student can use to develop problem-solving skills and decision-making and increase his ability to imagine and pay attention because it depends on contests and virtual games that encourage the student to compete to gain points in his knowledge and performance skills (Glover, 2013). According to the study (Deterding, Dixon, Khaled, & Nacke, 2011), gamification is a recent concept, as it was first documented in 2008, but it did not witness widespread differentiation before the second half of 2010. Zichermann & Cunningham (2011) defined gamification as using game mechanics based on thinking to engage and motivate individuals to learn and solve problems. Holloway (2018) also defined it as using game design to enhance non-game contexts by increasing participation, loyalty, and competition; they include points, certificates of appreciation, competitions, posters, and badges, and can be used in health care, commerce, and education.

Some researchers use learning platforms to support gamification in their teaching. In the study of Dominguez, Saenz-de-Navarrete, de-Marcos, Fernandez-Sanz, Pages, Martinez Herraiz, 2013, a gamification-based software was designed for an e-learning platform (Blackboard), and its quantitative and qualitative data showed an increase in students' motivation, which has an emotional and social impact on the students.

Gamification is appropriate for multiple teaching levels because it positively affects the success of the teaching mission by improving the levels of participation and motivation for students. It also helps in overcoming the complex academic challenges that learners face. Teachers can integrate this strategy with the curriculum to help bridge the gap between the negative stagnation in the learning process and students' active participation, which increases their academic achievement and the level of satisfaction with their performance (Kaufmann, 2018). Schaaf and Quinn (2019) used gamification in their nine years of experience and found that gamification effectively solves many common problems in classrooms, such as student participation, speaking time, differentiation, data tracking, and increased student achievement.

The study (Dicheva, Dichev, Agre, & Angelova, 2015; Majuri, Koivisto, & Hamari, 2018) showed that students engage in education better when education is based on the gamification environment and that the gamification strategy can be used as an illustration of complex concepts, through an online activity that includes the components of the concept. The learner must complete the e-learning activity by going through the game stages.

Kahoot is an educational application that supports the Arabic language. It is based on the game system that encourages the learner. It inspires enthusiasm and competition away from the classroom's traditional atmosphere, especially those who shyly avoid participating and engaging in front of their colleagues (Basif, 2017), this was confirmed by Pede (2017) that the Kahoot application improved the ability of students to comprehend scientific concepts, especially those who suffer from learning difficulties, as it contributed to an increase in students' outcomes from these concepts.

The study of Elshemy (2017) aimed to investigate gamification's impact on academic achievement and motivation among second-grade students in Muscat, Oman. Where the study sample reached (68) male and female students, who were divided equally into an experimental group and a control group, and a quasi-experimental approach was used to implement the study, the results showed that there are statistically significant differences between the experimental group and the control group in increasing the academic achievement in favor of the experimental group.

The study of (Mejia, 2013) indicated that the use of gamification through digital applications contribute to the learners' involvement in the learning process, and helps to attract learners to the learning process, and the possibility of using it at anytime and anywhere, and these applications also allow linking gamification to social networking sites, benefitting more from gamification in education. The study of Sauerland et al., 2015 found gamification's effectiveness in developing motivation and learning attitudes.

Rouse (2013) conducted a study to demonstrate the relationship between gamification, motivation, and microbiology achievement among community college students in America. It focused on methods that improve students' learning and motivation, leading to higher student graduation rates. The results showed a strong relationship between the study variables, as gamification's strategy increased the students' achievement and motivation.

While the study of Nah et al., 2013 confirmed the great effect of gambling in increasing the motivation of learners and thus increasing academic achievement, the study used two basic concepts: The first: (Deep attention and involvement), and the second: (Cognitive absorption), being the direct product of the use of gamification. The study also showed its impact on academic achievement. Because it is the indirect result of using digital game stimuli, the study also provided a general framework explaining the principles of gamification (direction to goal and achievement, reinforcement, competition, and fun direction), with gamification elements (points, badges, levels, leaders, challenges, etc.), cognitive absorption and engagement (modernity, repetition, continuity, pluralism, evaluation, passion, control, etc.). The most important recommendations of the Eleventh International Conference on Information and Communication Technology held in October 2016 in Indonesia were the necessity of employing learning arose by manipulating the educational process.

The rules and principles in the application of gamification help to make learning more relevant in the educational environment, which was adopted in the current study (Saunderson, 2011)

- Set goals to be specific and gradient in difficulty.
 - Provide frequent feedback, and clarify the progress that has occurred in their learning.
 - Collecting points after students complete the lessons successfully to advance to higher levels.
 - Each student's speed in answering, receiving feedback, and collecting points
 - Learning metrics for teachers to notice students with tools, as time spent, badges and levels.
- Measure progress to provide feedback and reward effort in proportion to the effort expended.

In extrapolating the future through a study conducted by the Pew Research Centers Internet & American Life Project, the study showed that about 53% of gamification would be widespread, and by 2020, there will be great progress in adopting and using gamification, which will have a great role to play in our daily activities. (Anderson & Rainie, 2012).

Based on the above role of gambling in science education, this study was conducted to reveal the impact of an educational environment based on gamification strategy through an educational platform in scientific acquisition concepts and the attitudes towards science among students of the second grade in Jordan.

The study Problem

In light of the technological revolution and recent global developments due to the Corona pandemic, teachers have needed to conduct learning through gamification that helps acquire scientific concepts and develop the attitudes towards science, especially at the basic stage and distance learning due to the Corona pandemic. Based on her experience, the researcher noticed weakness in the students' scientific concepts and their negative attitudes toward science and weakness in dealing with these concepts in their daily lives. Teachers of science courses face difficulties in teaching science for three primary grades, And based on feedback from field teachers, it was clear that there were lapses in the science subjects. Simultaneously, the International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) indicated a clear improvement in Jordan's students' average performance in the international study (TIMSS 2019) in the eighth-grade mathematics and science subjects. Compared to 2015, this level decreased (20 points compared to the year 2011). The test showed that Jordanian students' results for the year (2018) reached 400 points, which is less than the acceptable average of the Organization for Cooperation and Development, 489 points. This decline may be attributed to some of the methods and strategies of science education used in schools that depend on rote memorization; this led to ignoring the student's role in acquiring scientific knowledge and scientific concepts and its negativity in the educational position. Jordan ranked 59 in it, and the globally accepted rank is 24 (PISA, 2018). The learning environment through the educational platform based on gamification may be an effective technique for engaging students and improving science learning outcomes. Students in the present time interact, and their knowledge and behavior are affected by their continuous use of digital technologies.

The challenge (during the Corona pandemic) facing the educational system began to adapt to development to achieve equality between the student's daily life and learning conditions. The researcher noticed that the participation, enthusiasm, and positive attitude towards science are not lost, as the researcher noticed through her academic experience, the low academic performance of students in science generally, and scientific concepts and negative attitudes towards scientific subjects. That is why the study of Fabricatore & Lopez, 2014 suggested that using gamification to design learning activities positively affects learning environments and improves students' effective participation in learning activities with more positive academic achievement effects. The importance of research is to identify the effectiveness of an educational environment based on gamification strategy through an educational platform in the acquisition of scientific concepts and the attitudes towards science among second-grade students in Jordan.

Study questions

- 1- What is the effectiveness of an educational environment based on gamification strategy through an educational platform in acquiring scientific concepts for second-grade students?
- 2- What is the effectiveness of an educational environment based on gamification strategy through an educational platform in developing the attitude towards science among second-grade students?

Study hypotheses

- 1- There are no statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha=0.05$) between the mean scores of the second-grade students in the experimental and control group in testing scientific concepts due to the teaching method (gamification strategy and traditional methods).
- 2- There are no statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha=0.05$) between the average grades of the second-grade students in the experimental and control group in the approach to science scale due to the teaching method (gamification strategy and traditional methods).

Significance of the study

The study stemmed its theoretical significance from the following fields.

The current study is consistent with the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan's education attitudes regarding the need for less education and more learning during the Corona pandemic. A theoretical framework on e-learning activities was presented based on the gamification principle directed at students of the first grades. Providing information on the extent to which first-grade students interact with online activities directed at e-learning programs in light of the Corona pandemic and distance learning.

Application significance:

The current study results may be beneficial to curriculum authors by incorporating gamification strategy and technology principles into science curricula for all academic levels. The results of this study provide those in charge of qualifying and developing teachers during their service in the Ministry

of Education with new information and techniques that may contribute to the set up of training programs to raise the efficiency of teachers in teaching science.

Study limits and limitations:

- 1- Human limits: limited to a sample of second-grade students.
- 2- Spatial limits: It was conducted in the Al-Hejaz School of the Directorate of Education and Special Education in Amman.
- 3- Time limits: Conducted in the first semester of the 2020/2021 academic year.

The determinants of this generalization are represented by the following: The two tools of the study in light of available indicators of honesty and consistency and the respondents' objectivity.

Procedural definitions

- An educational platform: It is an online platform (Microsoft teams) hosted on the school website, which provided a set of interactive services for students' learning via the Internet, given the circumstances of the Corona pandemic, in a multimedia participatory way. Such as videos, animations, texts, and sounds, and based on gamification, the students in the experimental group are enabled to access the information and tools necessary to support the delivery of assignments and tests at the specified period.

Gamification: a set of actions that take place through the use of game items and components, such as points, badges, and leaderboards, to challenge students to take first place in the game (Vanolo, 2017, 15). The educational gamification environment is defined procedurally as the use of selected game elements that suit the nature of the educational material, which are developed according to procedures for second-grade students' advancement designed to achieve specific levels of learning and to obtain points when completing educational tasks within a specific period, in the form of activities carried out by students to acquire scientific concepts contained in the unity of living organisms and the development of attitudes toward science.

Scientific Concepts: It is a mental image that the learner develops about a specific scientific phenomenon with meaning or significance, as this individual can perceive, feel or link it to an indicative symbol, phrase, or term (Zaitoun, 2010: 233).

The acquisition of Scientific Concepts in this study is measured by the overall degree that the student attains in the researcher's scientific concepts test for this purpose.

Attitudes towards science: Zaitoun (1988, 13) defines it as a science-related concept that expresses the outcome of the individual's responses to a science topic in terms of student support or opposition to this topic: it is defined procedurally in this study by the student's feeling of acceptance or rejection and a willingness to learn science and enjoy it. In her studies, it is measured operationally by the degree obtained by students in measuring the attitudes towards science prepared by the researcher.

- Female students of the second grade: all female students enrolled in the first semester of the academic year (2020/2021) at the Hijaz School affiliated to the Directorate of Education and Special Education in Amman, and their ages range between (8-9) years.

Methodology

The semi-experimental method was used in this study, as this approach is appropriate for the study problem and serves its objectives.
sample of the study

The sample of the study consisted of (44) female students of the second grade, was chosen randomly and assigned into groups, experimental group (22) students were taught the content of the educational material (living beings) from the science book for the second grade using an educational environment based on the strategy of gamification. The education of the control group students and the number (22) students is on the same content of the educational material traditionally.

Groups equivalence

The scientific concept test, the scale of attitudes toward science, was applied before the study's commencement. The means and standard deviations were calculated, and their results showed a lack of statistically significant differences between the groups at the level of significance (0.05) between the means of the students' grades in the test as a whole, indicating the two groups' equivalence.

The study's instruments

To achieve the study's goals, the researcher prepared the following instruments.

- 1- The test of scientific concepts
- 2- Attitudes scale towards science.

Scientific Concepts Test:

The steps for preparing the test of acquiring scientific concepts:

- Review of the relevant research literature and previous studies related to its topic,
 - Analyzing the content of the third unit (living organisms) from the second-grade science book, identifying the scientific concepts included in them, as well as drafting and constructing test paragraphs to measure the ability of second-grade students to acquire scientific concepts, as the test included (22) multiple-choice questions with four alternatives. One of them is true.

The test time was calculated by calculating the arithmetic average of the first five students' response time and the last five students, so the appropriate time was approximately (37) minutes.

Scientific Concepts Test Validation:

- The validity of the test content was verified by presenting it in its initial form to a group of (11) specialized judges, including university professors specializing in science curricula and teaching methods, educational supervisors in the field of science, specialists in measurement and evaluation, and science teachers.

In light of the arbitrators' opinions and suggestions, 3 test items were deleted and replaced with three other items.

Test's reliability

- The test-retest method was used to check the test's reliability. It was applied on an expletory sample (25) students, out of the sample of the study, with an interval of two weeks between the two applications, and the reliability coefficient was calculated using the Pearson correlation coefficient, as the stability coefficient was (0.88), and the internal consistency method was used following the Kuder-Richardson equation 20, as the reliability coefficient was (0.79).

Construct validity to test the acquisition of scientific concepts:

The structural validity of the test was verified by calculating the Pearson correlation coefficient between the score of the paragraph with the total score of the test, as the results showed that the correlation coefficients of the test items with the total score of the test were positive and statistically significant, and these values are acceptable for the study, which indicates the existence of the structural validity of the test.

Determination of difficulty factors and discrimination: The difficulty factors ranged between (0.32-0.60), while the discrimination factors ranged between (0.33-0.75).

a measure of the attitudes towards science

- Drafting the paragraphs of the scale, the attitudes toward science, as it included (25) paragraphs that covered basic areas of science such as the importance of science, enjoying science, appreciating the efforts of the teacher and scientists.

As for the ranking, the triple Likert scale (agree, neutral, disagree) was used to measure the students' attitudes to achieving the topics presented in the scale related to the attitudes towards science.

The scale of the attitudes toward geometry

After reviewing related literature and previous studies, the researcher prepared an attitudes scale consisting of 25 items.

The validity of attitudes scale towards science

To achieve the scale validity, it was presented to a group of 15 arbitrators whose views regarding the items of the scale were taken into consideration.

In light of the referees' opinions and suggestions, (2) the paragraphs were deleted and replaced with (2) other paragraphs. The scale in its final form consists of 25 items, distributed to the following dimensions: The importance of science, interest, and enjoyment of science, appreciating the efforts of the teacher and scholars. Thus, the maximum score is 75, and the minimum is 25 degrees.

Construct validity for the attitudes toward science scale:

The scale's structural validity was verified by calculating the Pearson correlation coefficient between the score of the paragraph with the total score of the scale on the one hand and the score of the paragraph and the field to which the paragraph belongs on the other hand. Statistically, these values are acceptable for the purposes of the study, which indicates the existence of the structural validity of the scale.

Calculating the scale time was achieved by calculating the arithmetic average of the first five students' response time and the last five students, so the appropriate time was approximately 33 minutes.

Reliability of the attitudes scale towards science

To achieve the reliability of the scale, the test-retest method was used, as the scale was applied to a sample consisting of (25) from outside, the study sample with an interval of two weeks

between the two applications, and the reliability coefficient was calculated using the Pearson correlation coefficient, and the consistency method was also used. The procedure using the Cronbach Alpha equation and the following table shows the stability coefficients.

Table 1: Reliability coefficients

Field	Pearson correlation coefficient	Cronbach Alpha
The importance of science	0.77	0.74
Interest and enjoyment of science	0.85	0.80
Appreciate the efforts of the teacher and scholars	0.84	0.83
Total	0.88	0.78

The educational environment based on the strategy of gamification:

To design an educational environment based on the strategy of gamification and building it, the researcher took the following measures:

- Reviewing the theoretical literature and previous studies related to the subject of the study and its variables, reviewing the applications that are used to design the educational environment based on the strategy of gamification, determining the educational content, and analyzing its content, represented by the content of the unit (Living Organisms) from the second-grade science book.

Results of the Study

To answer the first question of the study, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations were calculated for the achievement of the two study groups on the post-scientific concept acquisition test and pre-marks, according to the teaching strategy (gamification through an educational platform, following the usual method), and the following table shows that:

Table 2: Means and standard deviations for the two study groups' achievement on post-scientific concept acquisition test and their pre-marks, according to the teaching strategy

The Group	Number	Maximum	Pre-application for testing		Post-application for testing	
			Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
The experimental group	22	22	11.45	3.70	16.36	2.44
the control group	22		10.68	4.16	11.68	3.46
Total	44		11.07	3.91	14.02	3.79

The previous table (2) shows an apparent difference between the two study groups' averages on post-application for testing, as the experimental group that conducted the study using the gamification strategy through an educational platform got a mean equal to (16.36). In contrast, the control group that was studied by the traditional method got a mean my arithmetic reaching (11.68). To ensure that the difference between the mean of the two study groups is statistically significant, at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), the one-way analysis of variance – ANOVA has been applied, and the following table shows those results.

Table 3: According to the teaching strategy, the results of the one-way analysis of variance – ANOVA for the differences in the achievement of the two groups on the post-scientific conceptual acquisition test

The source of variance	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	The average value of the sum of squares	value of (F)	level of significance	Eta value
Pre scientific concept acquisition	226.937	1	226.937	62.477	0.000	
Teaching strategy	194.422	1	194.422	53.525	0.000	0.566
The error	148.926	41	3.632			

Total 616.977 43

The previous table (3) shows the value of (F) calculated for the difference in the achievement of the two study groups on post scientific concept acquisition test according to the teaching strategy is equal to (53,525), which are the values of a function at the level of significance (0.000). Thus the difference between the two study groups on post scientific concept acquisition test was determined according to the teaching strategy of statistical significance. With this result, the first null hypothesis is rejected, which states that: "There are no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean scores of the second-grade students in the experimental and control group in the test of scientific concepts attributed to the teaching method (experimental strategy, and traditional methods)".

To identify the difference indicated in favor of any of the two groups, the modified arithmetic averages, and standard errors were extracted for the achievement of the two study groups, and table (4) indicates that difference.

Table 4: Means and standard errors of achievement of the two study groups on post scientific concept acquisition test according to the teaching strategy

The Group	Number	Maximum	Mean	Standard error
The experimental group	22	22	16.14	0.41
the control group	22		11.91	0.41

Table (4) shows that the experimental group that studied using the gamification strategy via an educational platform on a mean arithmetic rate is equal to (16.14). Finally, the control group's mean was studied by the traditional method, and its arithmetic means to 11.91; this indicates that the difference was in favor of the average of the experimental group. A comparison of its mean was made with the average of the control group; this confirms an educational environment's effectiveness based on gamification strategy through an educational platform in acquiring scientific concepts among second-grade students. Scientific concepts equal 0.566, which shows that 56.6% of the difference in the acquisition of scientific concepts is due to the teaching strategy, and the remainder of the difference in the acquisition of scientific concepts is equal to 43.4% due to other variables not covered by the current study.

The second question: What is the effectiveness of an educational environment based on gamification strategy through an educational platform in developing the attitudes towards science among students of the second grade of basic education?

Means and standard deviations were calculated to obtain the total score of the post-attitudes toward science scale and their pre-marks for the two groups, according to the teaching strategy of gambling through an educational platform (the traditional method), and the following table shows that:

Table 5: Means and standard deviations for the achievement of the two groups on the total score of the post-attitudes toward science scale and their pre-marks, according to the teaching strategy

The Group	Number	Maximum	Pre-application for testing		Post-application for testing	
			Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
The experimental group	22	75	28.68	7.25	41.27	8.74
the control group	22		29.73	7.48	33.55	6.41
Total	44		29.20	7.30	37.41	8.52

The previous table (5) shows an apparent difference between the two groups' averages on the science scale's post-attitudes. The experimental group that was taught using the gamification strategy through an educational platform got a mean equal to (41.27). In contrast, the control group that studied via the traditional method got a mean of 33.55, and to ensure that the difference between the mean of the two study groups is statistically significant, at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), the one-way analysis of variance – ANOVA has been applied, and the following table shows these results:

Table 6: One-way analysis of variance – ANOVA for differences in the achievement of the two study groups on the total score of the post-attitudes toward science scale according to the teaching strategy

The source of variance	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	The average sum of squares	Value of (F)	level of significance	Eta value η^2
Pre scientific concept acquisition	0.427	1	0.427	0.007	0.933	
Teaching strategy	655.792	1	655.792	10.906	0.002	0.21
The error	2465.391	41	60.131			
Total	3122.636	43				

The previous table (6) shows the (F) value calculated for the difference in the achievement of the two study groups on the total score of the post-attitudes science scale according to the teaching strategy was (10.906), which are significant values at the level (towards 0.002). Thus the difference between the two groups is on the total of post-attitudes toward science scale, and it is statistically significant according to the teaching strategy. Based on this result, the second hypothesis is rejected, which states that "There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the averages of the marks of the second-grade students in the experimental and control group in the attitudes toward science based on the teaching method (gamification strategy, and traditional methods)".

To identify that the difference indicates the benefit of any of the two groups, Means, and standard errors were extracted for the collection of the two study groups, and table (7) indicates that difference.

Table 7: Adjusted arithmetic averages and standard errors for the achievement of the two study groups on the total score of the post-attitudes toward science scale according to the teaching strategy

the field	The Group	Number	Maximum	Pre-application for testing		Post-application for testing	
				Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
The importance of science	The experimental group	22	24	9.05	2.36	13.09	2.69
	the control group	22		9.50	3.02	10.14	1.67
	Total	44		9.27	2.69	11.61	2.67
Interest and enjoyment of science	The experimental group	22	27	10.41	2.82	14.45	3.90
	the control group	22		10.64	2.65	12.18	2.61
	Total	44		10.52	2.71	13.32	3.48
Appreciate the efforts of the teacher and scholars	The experimental group	22	24	9.23	2.39	13.73	3.80
	the control group	22		9.59	2.50	11.23	2.94
	Total	44		9.41	2.42	12.48	3.59

Table (7) shows that the experimental group that was taught using the gamification strategy via an educational platform, on a mean equal to (41.28). Finally, the mean of the control group that studied via the traditional method was (33.54), which indicates that the difference was in favor of the mean of the experimental group compared to the average control group; this confirms the effectiveness of an educational environment based on the strategy of gamification through an educational platform in developing the attitudes toward science among second-grade students (0.21). This shows that 21% of the difference in science attitudes development is due to the teaching strategy. The remaining percentage of the difference in science attitudes development is equal to 79% due to other variables not covered by the current study.

Means and standard deviations were also calculated for the achievement of the two study groups on all post-attitudes toward science scale and pre-marks skills, according to the teaching strategy (gamification via an educational platform, the traditional method), and the following table shows that:

Table 8: Means and standard deviations of the achievement of the two study groups on all areas of post-attitudes towards science scale and pre-marks, according to the teaching strategy

The Group	Number	Maximum	Mean	Standard error
The experimental group	22	75	41.28	1.66
the control group	22		33.54	1.66

The previous table (8) indicates an apparent difference between the means of the two study groups on all areas of the post-attitudes toward science scale, as the experimental group that was taught using the gamification strategy through an educational platform got Means of the following three fields (13.09,14.45, 13.73), respectively. In contrast, the control group obtained Means of the following three fields (10.14, 12.18, 11.23), respectively, and to determine whether the differences between the averages of the two study groups were statistically significant at a significant level ($0.05 = \alpha$), a multivariate analysis of variance (MANCOVA) was applied, table (9) showed the results of the analysis of using the Wilks' Lambda test:

Table 9: Wilks' Lambda test results for differences between the performance of the two study groups according to the different teaching method on all areas of the post-attitudes toward science scale

Variable	The value	F-test	Degrees of freedom	level of significance
teaching strategy	0.685	5.683	3.000	0.003

It is evident from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences between the performance of the two study groups according to the method of teaching on the post-attitudes science scale, based on the value of the F-test (5.683), with a significance level (0.003), and the multivariate analysis of variance (MANCOVA) was applied.

The results of the analysis are shown in table (10):

Table 10: The multivariate analysis of variance (MANCOVA) for the performance of the two study groups on all areas of the post-attitudes toward science scale

The source of variance	The skill	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	The average sum of squares	value of (F)	level of significance	Eta value	The value of Wilks' Lambda
The pre-importance of science	The importance of science	2.192	1	2.192	0.449	0.507		.954
	Interest and enjoyment of science	2.557	1	2.557	0.232	0.632		
	Appreciate the efforts of the teacher and scholars	1.433	1	1.433	0.118	0.733		
The pre-interest and enjoyment of science	The importance of science	9.815	1	9.815	2.011	0.164		.935
	Interest and enjoyment of science	21.814	1	21.814	1.984	0.167		

	Appreciate the efforts of the teacher and scholars	6.100	1	6.100	0.501	0.483		
The pre-appreciate the efforts of the teacher and scholars	The importance of science	8.658	1	8.658	1.774	0.191		.893
	Interest and enjoyment of science	26.786	1	26.786	2.436	0.127		
	Appreciate the efforts of the teacher and scholars	0.052	1	0.052	0.004	0.948		
Teaching strategy	The importance of science	86.915	1	86.915	17.807	0.000	0.313	.685
	Interest and enjoyment of science	53.766	1	53.766	4.889	0.033	0.111	
	Appreciate the efforts of the teacher and scholars	67.686	1	67.686	5.555	0.024	0.125	
The error	The importance of science	190.356	39	4.881				
	Interest and enjoyment of science	428.875	39	10.997				
	Appreciate the efforts of the teacher and scholars	475.206	39	12.185				
Total	The importance of science	306.432	43					
	Interest and enjoyment of science	519.545	43					
	Appreciate the efforts of the teacher and scholars	552.977	43					

Table (10) indicates that the value of (F) for the teaching strategy for the field of importance of science reached (17.807), at 0.000 level of significance. For the field of interest and enjoyment of science, it reached (4.889), at the level of significance (0.033), and reached the field of appreciating the efforts of the teacher and scholars (5.555), at a level of significance (0.024). This indicates statistically significant differences between the averages of the two study groups' performance on all areas of the post-attitudes science scale. The second hypothesis is rejected at the level of the three domains to know which variable is favored by the difference, as the arithmetic averages were extracted for the performance of the two study groups, and table (11) shows those averages.

Table 11: Arithmetic averages and standard errors of the performance of the two study groups on all areas of the post-attitudes science scale

The skill	The Group	Number	Maximum	Arithmetic mean	standard error
The importance of science	The experimental group	22	24	13.03	0.47
	the control group	22		10.20	0.47
Interest and enjoyment of science	The experimental group	22	27	14.43	0.71
	the control group	22		12.21	0.71
Appreciate the efforts of the teacher and scholars	The experimental group	22	24	13.72	0.75
	the control group	22		11.23	0.75

Table (11) shows that the experimental group was taught using the gamification strategy through an educational platform on Means of the following three domains (14.43,13.03, 13.72), respectively. In contrast, the control group got Means for the following three domains (10.20, 12.21, 11.23) respectively, and this indicates that the difference was in favor of the average of the experimental group when comparing its averages with the averages of the control group, and this confirms the effectiveness of an educational environment based on the strategy of gamification through an educational platform in developing all areas of the attitudes science scale among second-grade students. ETA's value is squared, which expresses the size of the impact this strategy has had on science's importance (0.313) for the field of interest and enjoyment of science (0.111). For estimating the teacher and scientists (0.125), this shows the proportions of variation in these three skills as a result of the teaching strategy.

Discussion

The first question: What is the effectiveness of an educational environment based on gamification strategy through an educational platform in acquiring scientific concepts for second-grade students?

The variance between the averages of the students' scores on the test of acquiring scientific concepts showed that they are attributed to the method of teaching and for the benefit of students who studied according to the educational environment based on (gamification). It encourages students to practice learning from the ability to understand and academic achievement, as multimedia learning allowed them to manipulate through videos, animations, texts, and sounds. It allowed them to retrieve the knowledge they acquired and then build meaningful and re-link information to form a meaningful conceptual structure and help the learning environment interactive gamification based on providing them with the opportunity for self-learning. The educational environment allows students to view and repeat the content several times through the educational platform, such as Microsoft, which helped them increase scientific concepts. The environment has also provided interaction between students and the educational content more through questions and answers, which the researcher prepared within the Kahoot application and word wall.

The gamification method is one of the activities used in the science teaching process because it contains purposeful activities that include specific activities carried out by the teacher and students by following certain rules. Because of its many advantages for acquiring scientific concepts if the teacher makes the right choice and employs them to face the educational problems, e-learning, in light of the Corona pandemic, and providing knowledge, information, and skills through educational models preferred by students at this age.

These results agree with those of Ibanez et al., (2014), whose results showed a statistical indication that demonstrated improved learning, as agreed by a study (Tvarozek & Braz, 2014), whose results showed the positive effect of the proposed gamification elements on learning performance.

The study of Elshemy (2017), which showed the gamification environment's effectiveness in developing achievement, is also in agreement, and the study of Rouse (2013) showed the impact of gamification on achievement.

Discussing the results related to the second question: What is the effectiveness of an educational environment based on gamification strategy through an educational platform in developing the attitudes towards science among second-grade students?

The accompanying analysis of variance (ANCOVA) showed that there are statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the averages of students' performance on the scale of the attitudes toward science and in favor of the experimental group that was taught according to the strategy of gamification through an educational platform. This result can be explained by the teaching method according to gamification's strategy through an educational platform that leads to the development of thinking and allows the students to discuss and express opinions. This allows the students to express their opinion without embarrassment or fear by raising their interest and increasing their motivation to search for appropriate solutions by discussing information and creating a positive collective learning environment in which the students participate in discussion and dialogue. All of this contributed to increasing students' self-confidence, their desire to learn, research, and questioning to satisfy curiosity, and the practice of mental openness, all of which led to the development of attitudes towards science, as the results showed the effectiveness of an educational environment based on the strategy of gambling through an educational platform in developing the attitudes towards science among second-grade students. The main thing is that the value of ETA squared, which expresses the size of the impact that this strategy has had for the field of importance of science (0.313), for the field of interest and enjoyment of science (0.111), and for the field of estimating the efforts of teachers and scientists (0.125). This result is attributed to the impact of the educational environment and the conviction of parents of students [the importance of science, which affects their children's attitudes. This result is in agreement with the study of Sauerland et al., 2015; Rouse, 2013

Also, Nah et al. (2013) showed the great impact of gambling in increasing learners' motivation, thus improving academic achievement, which may be reflected in students' tendency towards science and thus their recognition of the importance of science and the appreciation of scholars.

Recommendations

In light of the results of the study; which showed the effectiveness of the educational environment based on the strategy of gamification in acquiring scientific concepts and developing the attitudes toward science among second-grade students, it recommends the following:

1. Science teachers using a strategy of gamification through educational platforms in their science teaching; due to their great effectiveness in acquiring scientific concepts and developing the attitudes toward science among students.
2. Educational supervisors by holding training courses and workshops for science teachers to train them in employing the strategy of gamification, through educational platforms in teaching science, especially during the period of educational crises such as the Corona pandemic
3. Those in charge of designing and writing science curricula in the Ministry of Education to focus on science books for this stage and on gamification principles in education and their inclusion in them, to be used in the teaching process.

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